

Australian Research Data Commons

Critical Health Data Needs Analysis

ARDC People Project Final Report

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1. Project Information

Project Code and Title	PE028: Environmental Health Critical Data Needs Analysis
Project DOI	
Project Start and End Dates	1 August 2025 – 30 April 2026
Reporting Period	30 April – 30 June 2026
Lead Contracting Organisation	The University of Canberra
Project Manager	Dr Timothy B Chaston
Partner Organisations	Queensland University of Technology, Curtin University, The University of Sydney, Australian Institute of Health and Welfare
Focus Area and Activity	People RDC Focus Area 1. FAIR Assets Activity 1.3 Government Data Assets

1.1 Background

Environmental health (EH) is a data driven research field that quantitates human health consequences of environmental hazards, their management and related government policies. EH analyses require health data to be

linked with spatially and/or temporally explicit exposure model simulations to quantitate human health effects, and the resulting exposure-response functions can then be used for a variety of purposes, including calculating health impacts of environmental exposures and establishing the economic benefits of policies that aim to promote environmental initiatives, such as Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). EH research can inform spatially and temporally targeted interventions that protect human and EH in a changing climate. Yet to maximise the opportunities for society, researchers and policy makers need access to comprehensive and coherent data infrastructure with data assets that are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reproducible (FAIR).

Environmental epidemiology is the study of unhealthy exposures and behaviors and their social, political and corporate determinants. By quantifying the population health effects of air pollution, industrial chemicals, climate change, and even the changing biosphere, we increasingly protect the environment by promoting the understanding of our connection to it. The ideal audience for such evidence is decision makers, people who decide whether or not the environments that we depend on will be devastated by the interests of a few, whether or not communities will be impoverished and disadvantaged for profit, whether or not our environments will be managed in favour of sustained public health. In practice, the field of EH has a mandate that promises to provide the evidence required to expose corporate and industrial activities for their macroeconomic irrationalities. As such the field is often engaged to estimate health, environmental and social costs that are externalised from the business ledger. Costs that local communities bear, often without knowing, for polluting industries and commercial activities. We can calculate how much is worth spending on responsible disposal of toxic waste, what is a reasonable spend on cleaner air, and what is the price of climate change. Other examples include the loss of ecosystems that support agriculture, air pollution from incinerators, pollution of drinking water, and even the disproportionate impacts of climate change on outdoor workers and underprivileged communities. If this mandate is to be met, confidence in EH associations and causal inference is essential. The often-legal discourse that determines whether and to what extent cooperate and commercial interests can extract resources from physical and social environments is so readily coerced in favour of exploitation. Environmental epidemiology promises guard rails, ideally in the form of irrefutable scientific evidence.

Confidence in EH evidence is therefore crucial for its use in environmental policy and regulatory decision making. In practice, the sources of that confidence include statistical power, quality and acuity of health data and precision of EH effect estimates.

Herein, we assemble a critical EH data needs analysis, aiming to identify and define health data needs and the barriers to optimal use by EH researchers. From the outset, we consider the use of aggregated health datasets for health impact assessments and cost benefit analyses but increasingly focus on the production of primary evidence using a range of cohort surveys with and without linkage to individual level geocoded administrative health and social data. These data are collected routinely by health care providers and large repositories are compiled and curated by state government departments of health. Currently, health data assets are made available for research via secure data linkage environments and services, which vary between jurisdictions. The Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW) has harmonised a selection of health data sets that could be used in EH research and hosts a national data linkage service: <https://www.aihw.gov.au/our-services/data-linkage>.

This project aims to identify health data assets and infrastructures that are core public sector dependencies of EH research, and to chart recommendations for future coordinated, comprehensive and coherent data infrastructure, assets, policies, governance and ethics processes that will better enable policy targeted health research, time sensitive health risk communication and systematic use of scientific evidence in policy and regulatory decision making.

1.2 Achievement of project aims

Aims:

- To improve understanding of the health data resources required to address key EH research scenarios.
- To define optimal health data governance, formatting and access infrastructures for EH research that address Australian environmental-public health policy priorities
- To enhance awareness of key infrastructure developments that would permit delivery of health and sociodemographic data at optimal spatial and temporal scales for precise environmental epidemiology
- To improve understanding of health data privacy risks and their mitigations for administrative data custodians and researchers
- To identify the barriers to trust and social license for the use of administrative health data by EH researchers

Activities:

The project team surveyed EH researchers who quantify relationships between environmental exposures and human health. We hosted a series of focused stakeholder meetings with representatives of EH research themes, specifically exploiting the expertise and knowledge of the existing HEAL communities of practice and its 10 research themes (<https://healnetwork.org.au/research-themes/>). Participants were chosen to represent a broad range of research disciplines and were approached with attention to their specific research interests and the intersection of those with administrative and other health data. After introducing the project and its aims, the meetings were structured around specific relevant publications demonstrating the use of administrative health data, followed by a horizon scanning exercise to establish future directions. Finally, participants were asked to reflect on their experiences of specific data infrastructures.

Further informal outreach was achieved through collegial networks and the current funded data infrastructure projects: The Clean Air and health Research Data and Analysis Technology ([CARDAT](#)), AusEnHealth ([AusEnHealth](#)) and Generation Victoria ([GenV - Generation Victoria](#)). These projects represent contrasting and complimentary approaches to developing data infrastructures for EH research and are exemplary of the current EH data landscape in Australia, providing critical context for the present analysis of health data infrastructures. Specifically, CARDAT was developed under funding from ARDC and hosts a range of derived and modelled datasets with a rapid credentialisation process. Under a grant from the Medical Research Futures Fund (\$2M), AusEnHealth explicitly partners with AIHW to investigate governance and access modalities for aggregated nationally consistent datasets with sufficient spatial and temporal resolution for quantitative assessments of EH relationships. GenV has established a linked individual level data asset with lifestyle and health surveys from all parents and live births in the state of Victoria; “GenV securely links information, assessments and samples with health and service data”. GenV has been formulated with a clear understanding of the health data landscape and the barriers it presents to timely and targeted EH research, particularly the precise discovery of epidemiological associations.

Concurrently, we performed a systematic mapping review to identify existing quantitative evidence of EH relationships in Australia and recruited corresponding authors for an online survey of health data needs. To test the extent to which existing Australian health data infrastructures dictate the quality and focus of EH research and its readiness to inform and moderate environmental policy and practice, we categorised included studies according to the health data assets

that were used to determine associations and the relevance of those associations to foreseeable environmental calamities and population health risks, as identified in our horizon scanning stakeholder engagement.

2. Project Delivery

2.1 Achievements against project work packages/deliverables:

Work Package 1 - Project Establishment Activities

- Recruited and engaged with scientific advisory board; endorsed terms of reference, held scientific advisory and governance meetings
- Applied for and received ethics approval from the University of Canberra Human Research Ethics Committee

Work Package 2 - Systematic Mapping Review

- Developed and executed a systematic review protocol with a database search strategy and inclusion/exclusion criteria (PROSPERO systematic mapping review protocol.pdf)
- Screened 2149 titles and abstracts and selected 211 for full text screening ([HDNA Database searches.docx](#)).
- Generated a table of data extracted from 38 articles meeting the stringent epidemiologic criteria, including details of exposure-response functions and the health data resources from which they were derived (See appendix 1).
- Narrative synthesis of the findings and recommendations for future health data driven EH research (section 3.2)

Work Package 3 – Stakeholder Engagement

- We held 8 horizon scanning sessions covering all EH themes across the HEAL network and reached out to proponents of 3 EH data infrastructures that are currently under various stages of development. Namely, CARDAT, AusEnHealth and Generation Victoria.

- We held two scientific advisory board workshops. The first established the focus and directions of the project and the second was structured around draft recommendations, which were workshopped to achieve consensus and final endorsement.

Please see monthly traffic light reports at [PE028 EHCritical Data Needs Analysis Traffic Light Report.xlsx](#).

3. Project Outputs, Outcomes and Impact Reporting

Outputs

Outputs (include link to output)	Usage Measure	Data Source/s	Baseline and Targets	Results, evidence, and summary of benefits to the research community
Output 1 <i>Stakeholder consultation across EH research themes and the broader Australian EH research community</i>	Acknowledgement of obstacles to health data use	AIHW	Baseline: EH research dictated by health data availability Target: EH priority research enabled by streamlined	See table 2 for summary of discussions See table 3 for key EH research scenarios and the datasets/infrastructure required to support them

Outputs (include link to output)	Usage Measure	Data Source/s	Baseline and Targets	Results, evidence, and summary of benefits to the research community
			data infrastructure	
Output 2 Systematic mapping review	Citations in scientific literature	AIHW, State administrative health data archives, Australian and international research communities	<p>Baseline: Data infrastructure primarily formulated around health data custodian risk aversion</p> <p>Target: Risk concessions for priority EH research evidence production.</p>	<p>Health data assets ranked on prevalence of use in publications: what has worked in the past and how were EH research topics dictated by health data resources?</p> <p>A table of key Australian EH research publications listing demonstrated environmental-health associations and the health datasets used to quantitate them.</p>

Outputs (include link to output)	Usage Measure	Data Source/s	Baseline and Targets	Results, evidence, and summary of benefits to the research community
<p>Output 3: Recommendations for Australian EH data infrastructures</p>	<p>Establishment of infrastructure enablers:</p> <p>Running-cost recovery fee structure on linkage environments;</p> <p>Adoption of Open Science Initiatives;</p> <p>Consolidation and linkage of cohort, the Person Level integrated Data Asset (PLIDA) and administrative health data;</p> <p>Standardised protocols for data</p>	<p>AIHW, State administrative health data archives, Australian and international research communities</p>	<p>Baseline: linkage subscription fees to recoup project costs.</p> <p>Targets: cost recovery only on administration of approvals and virtual machine compute resources.</p> <p>High precision exposure–outcome epidemiology feasible for 1-year, low</p>	<p>Recommendations to enhance access, resolution, format and quality, ethics approval, and data linkage for environment and health (datasets tailored to environmental–public health policy priorities</p> <p>Draft suggestions for additional needs to strengthen Australia’s national linked environmental and health data infrastructure to better support quantitative research on environmental exposures and</p>

Outputs (include link to output)	Usage Measure	Data Source/s	Baseline and Targets	Results, evidence, and summary of benefits to the research community
	approvals by data custodians.		budget (<\$100K) projects	Human health outcomes. See section 3.3: Recommendations for health data infrastructures

3.2 Systematic Mapping Review findings

Below is a summary of 38 studies outlining health data assets that were used, exposure outcome pairs, core evidence of associations (correlations from cross sectional studies and effect estimates from case-crossover and case-control studies) and the relevance of those associations to foreseeable environmental calamities and population health risks. To focus the review of literature on current administrative health data infrastructures, we applied the following inclusion and exclusion criteria in addition to those of the systematic mapping review:

- Published since 2021;
- Widely used Australian data asset with ongoing administration;
- Primary evidence of environmental—health effect estimate or correlation;
- Physical environmental exposures only;
- Published open access and uploaded as full text by Covidence or Endnote;
- Excluded studies of occupational exposures and one-off surveys.

Among selected studies, it is evident that Australia's EH research community are concerned about neighborhood and built environments. 13 studies demonstrate health associations with a range of physical and psychosocial morbidities. Tree canopy, green space and access to parkland are common subjects of recent EH studies, perhaps reflecting the perception that these exposures are modifiable features of Australia's urban areas and could be feasible climate adaptations following local to national policy and legislative interventions. This focus also suggests that EH researchers are increasingly aware of the socioeconomic and public health consequences relating to poor nutrition and obesogenic environments. Street connectivity, service accessibility and urban livability emerge as considerable predictors of lifestyle associated health outcomes.

Studies of seasonal and other weather anomalies, such as excessive heat, are also over represented in the present selection. It is demonstrated that diabetes and lifestyle related diseases are both effects and effect modifiers of heat-health relationships, along with cardio-respiratory mortality and morbidity, psycho behavioral outcomes and communicable disease rates. Overall the preponderance of climate relevant studies, both relating health to temperature exposures and to the environments that might mitigate those, suggests a rational perception of the need to provide evidence of the effectiveness of plausible climate adaptations. It is also notable that most of the present analyses include socioeconomic variables as mediators of reported exposure effects.

Only 6 studies from this selection report effects of air pollution or its proxies, such as persistent proximity to traffic.

In terms of health data sources, the Australian Diabetes, Obesity and Lifestyle Study was used in 3 of the present analyses, as relevant to built and urban environmental conditions, and their associations with metabolic disorders and chronic sedentariness. Similar sustained large cohort time series that were commonly used, likely without onerous access requirements, include Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia (HILDA) study, the Longitudinal Study of Australian Children (LSAC) and the Australian Longitudinal Study on Women's Health and the Health In Men Study (HIMS). The 45 and up study (Sax Institute) appears in 2 of the listed publications.

The Queensland Hospital Admitted Patient Data Collection (QHAPDC) was also frequently accessed for studies of climate exposures, along with other hospital data collections from Queensland Health. Other represented state/local administrative infrastructures include the Austin Hospital online Cerner database, Canberra Health Services, the Centre for Victorian Data Linkage (CVDL; various healthcare collections), the ABS, NSW Perinatal Data Collection,

the Western Australian Emergency Department Data Collection (EDDC) and Admitted Patient Data Collection (APDC) and the Australasian Severe Asthma Registry (ASAR).

Although the collection of studies in table 1 will be more representative when supplemented with the pool of eligible studies that were published behind paywalls, this mapping review suggests that Australian researchers are often reliant on holdable datasets from surveys of fully consenting cohorts, such as HILDA and the Australian Diabetes, Obesity and Lifestyle Study, or from carefully curated and negotiated aggregate health data sets, such as those available through CARDAT, the Victorian Public Health Survey (VPHS) and the Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS). Only 3 recent studies were performed using NSW, Victorian or Western Australian health data linkage environments, whereas Queensland Health linkage environments were used in 7 studies.

Table 1: Australian EH Literature published since 2021

Name	Email	Health data asset	DOI	Exposure	Outcome	Effect Estimate
Salma Ahmed	salma.ahmed@uq.edu.au	Australian Longitudinal Study on Women's Health	DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2021.107003 ^{1,2}	PM(2.5) (5.9-7.1 µg/m ³)	Child behavioural problems	1.27 (1.03-1.57)
Thomas Astell-Burt Xiaoqi Feng	thomas.astell-burt@sydney.edu.au xiaoqi.feng@unsw.edu.au	Mental health: 45 and up study	DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2020.106102 ³	≥30% vs <10% tree canopy	11 year risk of Dementia	0.86, (0.75-0.99)
Thomas Astell-Burt Xiaoqi Feng	thomas.astell-burt@sydney.edu.au xiaoqi.feng@unsw.edu.au	Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia	DOI: 10.1093/ije/dyab089 ⁴ DOI: 10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2019.8209 ⁵	≥30% tree canopy	Psychological distress	0.69 (0.54-0.88)

Anthony Barnett	Anthony.Barnett@acu.edu.au	Australian Diabetes, Obesity and Lifestyle Study	DOI: 10.1186/s12940-022-00894-4 ⁶	street intersection density, non-commercial land use mix, parkland and blue space	MetS status and metabolic profiles	Latent Class Analysis
Ang Li	ang.li5@unimelb.edu.au	Household, Income and Labour Dynamics in Australia Survey (HILDA)	DOI: 10.1016/j.lanwpc.2023.100734 ⁷	Energy poverty-can't heat home	Depression Anxiety Hypertension	1.49 (1.09–2.02) and 1.71, (1.13 – 2.58)
Tesfalidet Beyene, Erin Harvey Joseph van Buskirk	tesfalidet.beyene@newcastle.edu.au (T.B.); erin.harvey@newcastle.edu.au (E.S.H.)	Australasian Severe Asthma Registry (ASAR)	DOI: 10.3390/ijerph19127419 ⁸	Bushfire smoke	Breastfeeding Asthma	Ecological/cross sectional
Rachel Tham, Amanda J. Wheeler	Rachel Tham <rachel.tham@unimelb.edu.au>; Wheeler, Amanda (Environment, Aspendale)	Australian Diabetes, Obesity and Lifestyle 3 study	DOI: 10.1186/s12889-021-12375-3 ⁹	Neighbourhood percentage parkland	Cognitive Function	Ecological/cross sectional

	<amanda.wheeler@csiro.au>					
Bin Jalaludin	Bin.Jalaludin@health.nsw.gov.au	45 and Up Study and the Social and Environmental Factors (SEEF) Study	DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2019-028947 ¹⁰	Percentage Greenspace	Type II Diabetes	Ecological/cross sectional
Ning Ding	*nding@cmu.edu.cn	Social, Economic and Environmental Factors (SEEF) sub-study of the Sax Institute's 45 and Up Study	DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0164190 ¹¹	Heat and humidity	K10 high distress	Ecological/cross sectional
Carl Higgs	Carl.higgs@rmit.edu.au	Victorian Population Health Survey 2014 (VPHS)	DOI: 10.1038/s42949-021-00039-5 ¹²	Urban liveability index	Type 2 diabetes	0.90 (0.79–1.01)
Rongbin Xu	Rongbin.Xu@monash.edu.au	Queensland Hospital Admitted Patient Data Collection (QHAPDC)	DOI: 10.1088/1748-9326/abab33 ¹³	Cold and Hot	Cardiovascular mortality	1.32 (1.24–1.42) and 1.16 (1.07–1.26)
Shanshan Li	shanshan.li@monash.edu	Queensland Hospital Admitted Patient Data Collection (QHAPDC)	DOI: 10.1371/journal.pmed.1003176 ¹⁴	Cold and Hot	Cardiovascular hospitalisation	1.06 (1.04–1.09)
Michael Tong	Michael.Tong@anu.edu.au	Canberra Health Services	DOI: 10.1016/j.anzjph.2025.100296 ¹⁵	Cold and Hot 7 day lag	Emergency department presentations	1.067 (1.029 – 1.107) and 1.117

						(1.079 – 1.157)
Carol Lu Hunter	clhunter3@gmail.com	Comprehensive Epidemiological Dataset for Research, Innovation and Collaboration (CEDRIC)	DOI: 10.1111/ajag.70100 ¹⁶	Hot	Emergency department presentations	1.43 (1.33–1.54)
Clifford Afoakwa	c.foakwah@griffith.edu.au	Queensland Hospital Admitted Patient Data Collection (QHAPDC), Emergency Department Information System (EDIS) and the Registrar General Deaths Database (RG)	DOI: 10.1007/s10198-020-01198-5 ¹⁷	PM10	CVD diseases: Fatal Heart failure	1.026 (0.024)
Marko SIMUNO VIC	m.simunovic@qut.edu.au	Queensland Health Emergency Data Collection	DOI: 10.1111/1742-6723.13687 ¹⁸	Season and climate	Asthma ED visits	Incidence only
Edward Jegasothy	edward.jegasothy@sydney.edu.au	NSW Perinatal Data Collection Admitted Patient, Emergency Department Attendance and Deaths Register (APEDDR)	DOI: 10.1111/ppe.12822 ¹⁹ DOI 10.1007/s00484-017-1313-5 ²⁰	95 th percentile mean temperature	Preterm birth	1.43 (0.95–2.14)
Richard C. Franklin	richard.franklin@jcu.edu.au	Australian Bureau of Statistics (ABS; ICD-10: A00-Z99)	DOI: 10.1007/s00484-023-02430-6 ²¹	Excess Heat Factor	Mortality	1.05 (1.03–1.06)
K M Shahunja	k.shahunja@uq.net.au	Longitudinal Study of Australian Children (LSAC)	DOI: 10.1007/s40201-022-00824-z ²²	Persistent high traffic	asthma symptom trajectory	1.33 (1.17–1.50)

Wen-Qiang He	wen-qiang.he@sydney.edu.au,	Emergency Department Data Collection (EDDC) and Admitted Patient Data Collection (APDC)	http://publications.aap.org/pediatrics/article-pdf/155/1/e2024068183/1755256/ped.2024-00021.pdf ²³	Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI)	Infant ED visits	1.05 (1.03–1.07)
Jian Cheng	jiancheng_cchh@163.com	Queensland Hospital Admitted Data collection (QHAPDC) (https://www.health.qld.gov.au/hsu/collections/qhapdc)	DOI: 10.1093/ije/dyab155 ²⁴	Heat and Cold	Hospitalisations and deaths	1.19 (1.00–1.41)
Melvin B. Marzan	melvin.marzan@unimelb.edu.au	Collaborative Maternity and Newborn Dashboard (CoMaND)	DOI: 10.1111/1471-0528.18357 ²⁵	Food and built environment and SES	Gestational diabetes	Latent Class Analysis
Lucas Hertzog	hertzog@curtin.edu.au	Australian Clean Air Research Data Analysis Technology	DOI: 10.1136/bmjment-2024-301131 ²⁶	Heat anomalies	Suicide	Health Impact Assessment
Richard Franklin	richard.franklin@jcu.edu.au	Queensland Ambulance Service	DOI: 10.1017/S1049023X25101192 ²⁷	Excess Heat Factor	Mortality	1.14 (1.08–1.20)
C. Morley	cmmorley1@gmail.com	Pathology Queensland Gold Coast Laboratory database and Gold Coast Hospital and Health Service patient databases	DOI: 10.1017/S0950268818000614 ²⁸	Rainfall, humidity	Respiratory Syncytial Virus infections	Ecological/cross sectional
Christopher Bailey	chris.bailie@unimelb.edu.au	Victorian Department of Health Centre for Victorian Data Linkage	DOI: 10.1080/10962247.2022.2146810 ²⁹	PM2.5 daily	Weekly acute	1.043 (1.000)

					respiratory illness	- 1.089)
Takumi Abe	abe@tmig.or.jp	How Areas in Brisbane Influence health And acTivity" (HABITAT)	DOI: 10.1111/ggi.14253 ³⁰	Street connectivity	Frailty	1.27 (1.11-1.47)
Zhiwei Xu	xzw1011@gmail.com	Queensland Hospital Admitted Data collection (QHAPDC) (https://www.health.qld.gov.au/hsu/collections/qhapdc)	DOI: 10.1093/ije/dyab155 ²⁴	Heat and Cold	Acute myocardial infarction in diabetics	1.19 (1.00-1.41)
Muhammad A Sajjad	msajjad@barwonhealth.org.au	Victorian Admitted Episodes Dataset	DOI: 10.1136/bmjopen-2018-026880 ³¹	SES and accessibility	Diabetes related hospitalisations	2.14 (1.64-2.80)
Richard C Franklin	richard.franklin@jcu.edu.au	Queensland Emergency Data Collection	DOI: 10.1186/s12913-025-13777-4 ³²	Excess Heat Factor	Emergency Department Presentations	1.10 (1.10-1.11)
Thomas Nicholls	trnicholls92@gmail.com.	Austin Hospital online Cerner database	DOI: 10.1210/clinem/dgae820 ³³	Hi temperatures	Profound Hyponatremia admissions	Cross sectional
Yuming Guo	Yuming.Guo@monash.edu	Queensland Hospital Admitted Patient Data Collection (QHAPDC)	DOI: 10.1093/ije/dyab189 ³⁴	Heat	Urological disease hospitalisations	3.3% increase (2.9% - 3.7%)
Thomas Boissiere-O'Neill	t.boissiereoneill@uq.edu.au	Barwon Infant Study	DOI: 10.1038/s41370-025-00790-2 ³⁵	Early life exposure to	Allergic conditions; asthma in	1.08 (1.00-1.16)

				Phthalates and bisphenols	children under 5	
Elizabeth H. Lim	Elizabeth.lim@uwa.edu.au jane.heyworth@uwa.edu.au	Health In Men Study (HIMS)	DOI: 10.1038/s41416-023-02411-x ³⁶	PM2.5 and Black Carbon	Lung cancer	1.23 (0.97–1.54)
Tilda N Thomson	tilda.thomson@anu.edu.au	Victorian Emergency Minimum Dataset; VEMD	DOI: 10.5694/mja2.52364 ³⁷	Heat health alerts	Hospitalisation for COPD and diabetes related disorders	1.09 (1.03–1.16) and 1.27 (1.06–1.53)
Maria Soloveva	Maria.Soloveva@acu.edu.au	Australian Diabetes, Obesity and Lifestyle Study (AusDiab)	DOI: 10.1080/23748834.2024.2356408 ³⁸	Neighbourhood environment attributes	Depressive symptoms	Ecological

3.3 Stakeholder Consultation and Recommendations

HEAL Theme	Identified health data needs	Major concerns
Indigenous Knowledge Systems	Healthy country indicators and indigenous knowledge systems	Extractive approaches and history undermining trust
Health Systems Resilience and Sustainability	Carbon footprint data: consumables use and production costs (category 3 CO2 emissions) disaggregated to local health district or hospital/institution level.	Administrative data bases hold healthcare cost data, such as the Victorian Cost Data Collection and The National Hospital Cost Data Collection but not disaggregated consumable use data
Bushfires, Air Pollution and Extreme Weather Events	SURE space/data linkage environments data for precision of exposure-outcome testing and control of confounding with cohort survey data.	Access timelines for individual level data in secure environments. Datasets include geocoded unit records of deaths and hospitalisations for cardiorespiratory diseases. For optimally aggregated datasets; trust in academic systems of data governance and privacy protection; reassurance of custodians that re-identification through synthetic dataset constructs can be managed appropriately.
Food, Soil and Water Security	Farm animal health data, infectious disease data	No integrated data infrastructure for zoonotic disease: human and animal health data are siloed

Biosecurity and Emerging Infections	Animal (vector) data. Infectious disease register and hospitalisations, migration and population mobility	Statistical area 2 too big for infectious disease transmission studies. Ideally real time data needed for epidemics. https://ardc.edu.au/program/disease-data-challenges/
Urban Health and Built Environment	Household, Income, and Labor Dynamic Australia time series and other interview/self reporting survey data.	Few project timelines can accommodate the long lead time of access to linkage environments.(e.g. Centre for Victorian Data Linkage and the NSW Centre for Health Record Linkage)
Rural and Remote Health	Primary health services. Household, Income, and Labor Dynamic Australia, GP data: Electronic Medical Records	Impossible time requirements for access to data from Aboriginal Controlled Community Health Organisation (ACCHOs) and from Electronic Medical Records; geographical boundaries used for health data are incongruous with natural disaster affected areas.
At-risk Populations and Life Course Solutions	Linkage to individual data from ABS for SES stratified analyses. Data such as PLIDA	There is a strong will to demonstrate the political and social determinants of disease among low SES communities, as these represent environmental justice interventions that could yield cost effective co-benefits for society and the environment
Data and Decision Support Systems	AusEnHealth and CARDAT want to host data aggregates with novel trade-offs of temporal and geographical resolution.	Novel trade-offs of temporal and geographical resolution triggering risk aversion at AIHW.

Table 2: Heal research themes, data needs and major concerns

Environmental Priorities	Research scenarios	Data requirements
Indigenous welfare and environmental justice	Spatially targeted co-analyses of social and physical environmental exposures and their synergistic harms	Person level census (PLIDA) and annualised health data (NHDH): linkage infrastructure that can support low budget projects. Improved health data infrastructure in SA and NT, and national streamlining of ACCHOs data.
Bushfires and planned burns	Increased frequency of megafires exacerbated by climate change and ill-informed fire risk management	Daily mortality and morbidity at affected localities: linked cohort and administrative data. Health outcomes data aggregated only to the point of viable privacy risk at the ends of the time (daily: multiyear) – space (SA1: SA4) trade off.
Floods	Increased flood affected areas exacerbated by increasing inequity	Health and sociodemographic data in flood plain boundaries. Linkage infrastructure that can support low budget, short timeline projects
Vector borne disease	Climate driven changes in disease vector habitats, survival and transmission activity	Geographical and temporal harmonisation of farm animal health data, infectious disease data, and human population and health data.
Biosecurity and Emerging Infections	Farm animal epidemics, climate and globalisation increasing the risk of zoonotic virus pandemics	Zoonotic disease data, immigration and travel history, real time human health and immunisation surveillance data

Extreme heat	<p>Climate driven increase in heat related health care utilisation, particularly in low income areas: many practicable urban interventions for research analysis: greening, building regulations, energy transition, climate refuges for vulnerable people</p>	<p>Daily mortality and morbidity at affected localities: linked cohort and administrative data. Health outcomes data aggregated only to the point of viable privacy risk at the extremes of the time (daily: multiyear) – space (SA1: SA4) trade-offs.</p>
Ecosystem services collapse	<p>Climate and inequity driven increases in the prevalence and impacts of food insecurity among disadvantaged Australian households and communities.</p> <p>Reduced aquatic biodiversity due to droughts, surface water flow interruptions and pollution, and proliferation of environmental anti-microbial resistance</p>	<p>Person level census (PLIDA) and annualised health data</p> <p>Incidences of antimicrobial resistance in hospital and surgical care settings.</p>

Table 3. Key EH research scenarios and the datasets/infrastructure required to support them

3.4 Horizon scanning

We convened a total of 10 meetings with HEAL theme leads and their senior postdocs. The research themes cover a broad range of disciplines, and are ideally investigated using data collected from health care systems and services. Common to all EH researchers is the intention to inform policy and regulatory interventions that will ultimately reduce inequity, EH burdens and anthropogenic drivers of climate change. The AIHW was represented at all meetings.

Indigenous Knowledge systems

Research into indigenous health and knowledge systems may involve a variety of health care data, but also healthy country indicators and indigenous knowledge systems. 'Indigenous Data' refers to information or knowledge, in any format or medium, which is about and may affect Indigenous peoples both collectively and individually (<https://indigenusdatalab.org/care-data-maturity-model/>).

To address research data needs, these researchers combine themes of Indigenous data sovereignty and western health data systems with the aim of facilitating research that builds the case for Indigenous environmental custodianship and cultural practices on one hand, and Indigenous health in Australia's political, social and procedural environments on the other.

Central concerns for institutionalised data infrastructures were similar to those addressed by the [Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities | ARDC](#) project, as follows:

- Principles of Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics (CARE) for indigenous health and well-being data and care for country knowledge systems data;
- Colonial exploitative approaches, perpetrated often without malice, by researchers and government organisations seeking to do research on Indigenous communities;
- Breaches of personal data sovereignty;
Failure to demonstrate value for participating communities
- Social license and trust must be earned by respecting traditional customs and ways of being
- Traditional ecological knowledge (TEK) is crucial to the management of Australian flammable landscapes and reducing carbon emissions.
- Harnessing such knowledge systems and harmonising with colonial administrative systems can only be achieved by adhering to a dedicated governance framework that is also instructive of cultural safety ([Framework for Governance of Indigenous Data | NIAA](#)).

Health systems resilience and sustainability

Researchers in this field perform life cycle and carbon accounting analyses of hospital and health care systems. The intention is to reduce environmental impacts, look at alternative care approaches and compare outcomes. Although

digital health technologies and patient record linkage are likely inputs, analyses of carbon emissions and health system sustainability additionally require records of consumable production costs and volumes of use. This work aims to identify and target carbon intensive health care facilities in space and time and is important because commercial entities tend to hide their carbon footprints. Access to routinely collected health care consumables data would allow studies that identify the health care sectors of greatest environment impact, such as hospital care. This research theme also promises to determine the benefits of telehealth versus in-person consultations and the consequent burden of pathology requests and evaluate the cost benefit ratio of cancer screening programs.

Key data needs are as follows:

- Disaggregated consumable use estimates by clinic, hospital and jurisdiction;
- Granular records of diagnostic and prophylactic tests and surgeries;
- Administrative data bases with consumable use data;
- Age- and stage-specific prostate cancer incidence and mortality rates from registries, such as the NSW Cancer Registry (NSWCR);
- Cancer marker testing data from large international trials, such as the European Randomized Study of Screening for Prostate Cancer (ERSPC16) and the Prostate, Lung, Colorectal, and Ovarian (PLCO) Cancer Screening Trial.³⁹

Bushfires, Air Pollution and Extreme Weather Events

Researchers of this theme calculate exposure response functions using various data, but ideally need geocoded person level data, such as hospitalizations, emergency call outs, and unit cause of death records. The Secure Unified Research Environment (SURE) space/data linkage environment hosted by the Sax Institute has been used several times by this group, allowing precision of exposure-outcome testing and control of confounding with cohort survey data. Notable challenges were discussed as follows:

- Access timelines for individual level data in secure environments precludes small contracts/projects.
- Linkage environments are also initially daunting, intimidating and frustrating.

- Often project timelines prohibit precise environmental epidemiology studies.
- Data access conditions are prohibitive of ad hoc small projects designed to answer high priority decision needs.
- The ABS datalab space is another secure environment that may be underutilized (PLIDA) and it is quicker to get access especially if the project is up and running.
- ABS training sessions for five safes facilitates trust that researchers follow confidentiality guidelines.

The conversation turned to what can be done with freely available aggregated data resources, again highlighting the importance of non-secure data repositories and platforms, such as the AIHW Geography and time-specific health data for environmental analysis ([Hospitalisations data - Australian Institute of Health and Welfare](#)). Many high priority policy questions can be addressed using effect estimates derived from lowered-risk datasets, and the loss of epidemiological precision can be mitigated with bespoke tradeoffs of temporal and spatial aggregation. But for transparency, a series of minimum privacy requirements, such as suppression thresholds and proportionality of time-space resolution tradeoffs could be provided to reassure custodians and remove any need for discretionary risk aversion.

Challenges to the poignant application of this approach include the following:

- Health data are ideally aggregated to the lowest possible time and spatial units
- Suppression of low counts is a trade-off
- Privacy laws are interpreted variously across jurisdictions; data approvals are given only under the most risk averse interpretation.
- Custodian approvals for novel health data aggregates are often discretionary and over cautious
- Custodians and researchers are cautious about subject re-identification through synthesis of diverse data aggregates with juxtaposed time, space and demographic resolution.
- Streamlining and standardizing the custodian approvals process could be a very helpful intervention.

Food, Soil and Water Security

The meeting emphasised linking environmental, human, and animal health data to improve public health insights. Data integration challenges were a recurring theme. For example, although some national surveillance systems exist (e.g., for vector-borne diseases), zoonotic, environmental, and agricultural data are fragmented, difficult to link, and often

constrained by legal, institutional, or commercial barriers. Similarly, environmental hazards such as algal blooms and water contamination are monitored, but linking them to health outcomes is difficult, particularly in short timeframes.

The NHDH may offer opportunities to address this, but with complex approvals and limited scope for survey data.

The subject matter experts spoke of the following research scenarios:

- It is evident that green space delivers measurable health and economic benefits, suggesting both population-level data (e.g., CVD, mental health, medication use) and individual-level studies could strengthen understanding; even small interventions like home vegetable gardens may improve outcomes.
- Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is a One Health issue. Key risks include contaminated water, fresh food supply chains, and agricultural practices that drive AMR. Measurement of these human health risks requires integration of hospital, environmental, and agricultural data. Critical data gaps remain, especially around occupational exposure and individual histories.

There was discussion of emerging solutions, including wastewater surveillance and potential roles for the Australian CDC, though current priorities focus more on vaccines and disease surveillance than full data integration. Overall, the group agreed that better governance, cross-sector collaboration, and combined datasets are essential to address interconnected food, water and soil risks and their EH impacts.

Biosecurity and Emerging Infections

The discussion focused on challenges and opportunities in linking EH data with infectious disease outcomes, particularly in Australia and comparable international settings. Data governance and political constraints were recurring themes. The following specific challenges were noted:

- Work continues with COVID-19 case data from state health departments, but for risk assessment under a One Health framework environmental datasets need to be better linked with communicable disease outcomes, such as waterborne, vector-borne and respiratory infections.
- While large volumes of environmental data exist, issues of data quality, access, and timeliness remain significant barriers.

- Access to human health surveillance data is often slow, restricted by approvals, limited geographic resolution, and inconsistencies across states, which complicates national-scale research and timely responses.
- In some international contexts, human health data can be easier to access, particularly in field-based research settings. Similar challenges persist around environmental, vector and animal health data ([Animalhealthaustralia](#)), which are often low resolution or incomplete (e.g., for mosquitoes, pigs, or birds in Japanese encephalitis studies) and are siloed.
- In Australia, spatial resolution is a major limitation; commonly used units like SA2 are too coarse to capture environmental heterogeneity, leading to noisy analyses and risks of ecological fallacy.
- Critical metadata, such as travel history, immunisation status, and population mobility, are often missing or difficult to access, despite their importance for understanding disease transmission, especially in returning travellers or migrant populations.
- Access to detailed datasets (e.g., COVID-19 cases linked to vaccination status) has been inconsistent and sometimes influenced by policy considerations, with limited transparency around approval decisions. Delays of six to twelve months are common, hindering rapid public health responses.
- While national systems like the NNDSS and the Australian Immunisation Register exist, integration across datasets remains limited.
- Emerging approaches such as synthetic data and differential privacy offer partial solutions, enabling pattern analysis while protecting confidentiality, though they are not suitable for all epidemiological questions.

Participants noted growing potential in alternative data sources and infrastructure, including wastewater surveillance, mobile phone mobility data, pharmacy records, and real-time clinical datasets (e.g., through initiatives like the Queensland Digital Health Centre). Environmental and ecological datasets (e.g., via TERN) also provide opportunities for zoonotic disease research. However, access to these data, particularly from private sources like telecommunications companies, remains challenging.

Overall, the group emphasised the need for higher-resolution, better-integrated, and more accessible data systems to support EH research. There was support for decentralised data infrastructure, improved governance frameworks, and a potential role for the Australian CDC in enabling real-time data access and cross-sector integration. The discussion concluded that while technical capability is advancing, cultural, administrative and political barriers remain key constraints on progress.

Urban Health and Built Environment

The discussion centred on the strengths, limitations and practical challenges of working with various Australian and international datasets for health research.

Participating researchers highlighted the value of the HILDA survey, noting its high response rate and longitudinal cohort design. While it relies on self-reported measures, including self-diagnosed conditions, HILDA performs well in capturing mental health and quality-of-life outcomes. HILDA has also been linked to mortality data, and a restricted-access version is available for more detailed analyses. The British Household Panel Survey (BHPS) was also identified as similarly easy to access, though somewhat dated. Despite relying on self-reporting, certain measures, such as visible mould, were considered particularly sensitive and useful. The following limitations of surveys like HILDA for primary evidence production were noted:

- Geographic granularity and sample size; SA1-level geography would be preferable.
- For covariates, researchers often use proxies such as centroids or aggregate data at the SA3 level from the ABS.
- The relatively small national sample (around 17,000 individuals) further constrains analysis.
- Disaster exposure data, typically self-reported, can be enriched through integration with external sources, though environmental data linked via latitude and longitude can be difficult to merge effectively.

Linkage to other datasets was a recurring theme. Datasets containing externally reported or “hard” health endpoints, such as service utilisation or medication records, are preferable to self-reporting only. Medicare Benefits Schedule (MBS) and Pharmaceutical Benefits Scheme (PBS) data is particularly valuable for capturing time-varying health service use and medication patterns and the Centre for Health Record Linkage (CheReL) is an exemplary resource time and funds permitting. Suggestions for improved data infrastructures included the following:

- Broader harmonisation, such as through a national dataset like the NHDH, would be highly beneficial if it could unify records across all healthcare encounters.
Longitudinal datasets in areas like women’s health already integrate environmental exposures such as pollution and noise before providing linked data to researchers.

- Data access timelines pose a major challenge. Working with the CVDL (Custodian Data Linkage system) was too slow to meet project deadlines, forcing researchers to pursue alternative approaches.
- Feasibility of systems like CVDL or NHDH depends on whether access can be granted within a reasonable timeframe. Other datasets, such as SA-NT health data, were considered too limited due to weak links between socioeconomic status and health variables.

Synthetic datasets were discussed, noting that some ABS data at the SA1 level is already modelled in this way. A key concern is the lack of transparency around the methods used to generate synthetic data, which complicates interpretation and communication, especially with public or advocacy audiences. While synthetic data can be useful when no other data are available, and initiatives like those from the University of Canberra or AURIN provide helpful tools, there is a need for clearer methodological documentation.

Finally, the group noted the importance of non-health datasets, particularly those related to housing and built environments. Building and dwelling data, as well as information on infrastructure such as fire and police stations, were seen as valuable for analysing the impacts of building codes and broader environmental determinants of health.

Rural and Remote Health

Rural health inequities are central focus of this research theme and their research highlights how climate-related disasters exacerbate health inequities. Research in this theme demonstrates how data can influence policy and advocacy. For example, spatial analyses combining flood maps with socioeconomic data revealed disproportionately high impacts on disadvantaged populations, supporting submissions and funding bids. Similarly, targeted epidemiological studies, often enabled through partnerships and access to internal health service data, have helped communities advocate for resources. In another study, research on flood-related displacement showed very high PTSD risk, highlighting the need for better displacement data to support service planning.

The discussion highlighted significant challenges in accessing and integrating health data, particularly in rural, remote, and Aboriginal community–controlled settings. While national initiatives and datasets exist (e.g., through AIHW), consistent access remains limited. Moreover, researchers are rarely granted access to linked systems for clinical data.

Disasters have exposed these weaknesses, forcing rapid, improvised responses without established data-sharing frameworks.

Data needs and barriers were revealed as follows:

- A major research project in NT and SA was delayed by 2.5 years securing linked health outcomes data, leaving little time for analysis. Another was delayed accessing the NSW eMaternity database (1.5 years).
- Primary healthcare data in the NT is especially fragmented, with multiple custodians (including ACCHOs) and no centralised, research-accessible dataset.
- Efforts to understand how GP and allied health services influence emergency department and hospital use are hindered by fragmented systems, especially among private providers using diverse electronic medical records (EMRs).
- Data from recovery services are often withheld despite being used internally to justify funding.
- In regional areas across the country, health outcomes vary widely, driven by limited service access, workforce shortages, distance and challenges in aged care.

Participants recommended the following:

- A single entry point for data access across NT Health and ACCHOs would be highly beneficial; addressing the key barriers of capacity and governance will be crucial, particularly for smaller services.
- Support for the evolving Indigenous data governance area, and frameworks such as CARE principles; Cohesive systems for primary care data integration.

Overall, the discussion underscored longstanding issues of data fragmentation, slow access, limited governance capacity, and inequities in rural and Indigenous health contexts. While there are clear opportunities for better integration and use of data—particularly for planning, evaluation, and advocacy—systemic, institutional, and technical barriers continue to constrain progress.

At-risk Populations and Life Course Solutions

The discussion centred on the practical and conceptual challenges of conducting EH and social epidemiology research, particularly around data access and equity, and the limits of traditional analytical approaches in addressing inequalities. For example, estimating heatwave-attributable mortality and its relationship to social inequality is not possible using publicly accessible datasets. The research theme is exemplified by the following statement: “Inequality is not simply an effect modifier but a fundamental driver of both exposure and vulnerability. As such, interventions that do not address structural inequities, such as income, housing, and tenancy conditions, are likely to benefit more advantaged groups disproportionately.” The causal relationships that underly socioeconomic disparities in health outcomes are already well understood, and further complex modelling may add little value. Instead, the root causes are political and structural, and epidemiology risks overemphasising technical analyses at the expense of actionable insight. What data analyses could be used to support interventions that target exposure (e.g., environmental risks) and address underlying structural drivers (e.g., income redistribution, housing security)? Environmental exposures are often difficult to modify without broader systemic change, whereas vulnerability—shaped by social conditions—is more amenable to intervention. Examples included improving tenancy rights, increasing income, and addressing inequities in access to cooling during heatwaves. Participants also noted that some interventions framed as equitable (e.g., clean energy transitions) may still disproportionately benefit wealthier populations unless explicitly designed otherwise.

Specific data use barriers were indicated as follows:

- Access to linked data is more straightforward in public institutions.
- Academic research is often shaped by what data and resources are available, resulting in pragmatic, rather than ideal, study designs.
- Access pathways are often facilitated by strong collaborations, but barriers remain significant.
- While institutions like AIHW hold valuable datasets, access is inconsistent, costly, and administratively complex, particularly for unit-record data.

Specific suggestions were as follows:

- More usable intermediate products, such as well-structured aggregate datasets

- Linking socioeconomic indicators (e.g., SEIFA) with individual-level data
- Analysing patterns of unequal exposure as statistical modifiers, and as indicators of deeper structural inequities.

Overall, the conversation called for a shift in EH research toward greater emphasis on social justice, structural determinants, and policy-relevant interventions, alongside improved data access and stronger collaborative practices.

Clean Air and health Research Data and Analysis Technology

The Clean Air and health Research Data and Analysis Technology (CARDAT) platform is a collection of IT infrastructure that enables easy data sharing and reuse and supports reproducible data analysis. This online research platform collates a wide array of population, health and environmental datasets alongside a collection of analysis tools and methodology resources.

CARDAT is overseen by the [Centre for Safe Air](#) (CSA) and [WHO Collaborating Centre for Climate Change and Health Impact Assessment](#) (WHOCC-CCHIA). Its mission is to provide data, methods and tools to support research and analysis in the fields of air pollution, energy and health.

CARDAT resources are used widely by EH researchers and has achieved significant milestones off the back of ARDC funded projects (<https://cardat.github.io/air-health-data-bridges/>)

Australian Environmental Health (AusEnHealth) Project

Our environment critically affects our health, but to manage this we need access to data at a place-based level. This project will create an open interactive infrastructure, "AusEnHealth", that integrates and analyses environmental, health and sociodemographic data for each location across Australia. Through six use cases defined by our health organisation partners, AusEnHealth will be a critical national digital asset that meets urgent needs of researchers, health managers, policy makers, commercial entities and the public. Outcomes will include significantly improved place-based health and health resource planning, potential new targeted health products, more cost-effective environmental mitigation strategies and healthier Australians.

AusEnHealth promises to produce a single public platform through which health agencies, government departments, researchers, businesses and the community can access relevant health and environmental data to understand links between health and environmental hazards at a local level, predict current and future vulnerabilities, undertake scenario assessments to evaluate impacts and mitigation options, and develop more cost-effective policies and businesses for vulnerable populations in specific geographic regions across Australia.

Federated learning technology

AusEnHealth is a partnership with AIHW, through which health data access, both as novel data aggregates and via individual level linkage, will enable health impact assessments of policy and regulatory scenarios relating to changes in air pollution, climate readiness, and vector borne and infectious disease risks. The MRFF funded project will also explore and validate federated learning algorithms that promise to enable primary evidence production by establishing a distributed network of health data clients and training environmental-health models without moving the raw data. This machine learning approach could revolutionise the health data landscape and privacy protection technology.⁴⁰

Generation Victoria (GenV): Critical Infrastructure for EH Research

GenV is designed as a population-embedded lifecourse platform comprising over 125,000 Victorians (~50,000 children born 2021-23 and their parents) representing approximately 30% of Victoria's birthing population and broadly representative of Australian children and pre-midlife adults on ethnicity, disadvantage, urban/regional location and service use. GenV is designed to sit within a single state system, linking participants across Victoria's health, education and social services. This allows GenV to follow families across the places and services that shape their health and development.

It is Australia's only cohort of this scale and the only major birth cohort launched globally during the COVID-19 pandemic, filling a void left by the closure of comparable US and UK cohorts in the 2010s. GenV's first public data access is planned for 2026, making it immediately accessible to the EH research community. By embedding ~30% of a generation across the whole state, GenV is becoming a practical, population level life-course resource for prevention science.

For EH research specifically, GenV applies this population embedded, state wide model to track exposures and environments across the life-course. It addresses critical data needs that no other Australian dataset meets at the same time. Because participants are linked across Victoria's unified health, education and social service systems, GenV can support individual level, spatially and temporally resolved exposure modelling and cumulative exposure assessment. This allows researchers to study how environmental exposures and health trajectories interact as families move through different places, services and life stages.

Spatiotemporal exposure linkage at individual GenV participants can be linked to address-level environmental exposure data across the life course, enabling spatially and temporally explicit exposure models. This is a core requirement for EH research and is rarely possible at scale in Australia. Indicators already constructed at birth include air pollution, greenspace, food environment and area-level disadvantage, with more in development across multiple ages. When combined with My Geosome's address-level indicators, GenV allows exposure-response relationships to be estimated with a precision and individual-level resolution unavailable elsewhere in Australia.

Linked health data across Victorian and national systems GenV is linked to the CVDL, providing access to longitudinal Victorian administrative health records across longitudinal administrative collections, including perinatal data (VPDC), hospitalisations (VAED) and emergency presentations (VEMD). Some datasets extend back to 1993. GenV-linked state administrative data will be available to researchers from 2026 through the CVDL secure research environment. Additional linkage to national data assets (eg ABS PLIDA, AIHW NHDH) is planned, adding primary care, medicines use, social mobility, internal migration and socioeconomic indicators. Together, these linkages provide continuous, population-level health outcome data between GenV collection waves and support cumulative exposure-response modelling over time.

Longitudinal design across critical developmental windows GenV follows children and parents prospectively across early childhood and pre-midlife - life stages where environmental exposures strongly influence chronic disease, neurodevelopment and mental health. GenV is 'measuring the curve to change the curve': planned face-to-face phenomic waves every 5 years will show how exposures and events (such as preventive interventions or disasters) shift trajectories toward later burdens such as cardiometabolic disease, mental ill-health, cancer, and learning outcomes. GenV's multilingual digital survey system can deploy targeted surveys to volunteer subgroups at any time, enabling rapid collection of self-reported exposures such as residential history, occupational exposures, indoor environment and climate-related experiences.

Biological samples with relevance to EH GenV holds one of Australia's largest collections of population-representative biological samples, including antenatal and perinatal biosamples (pregnancy serum and plasma, newborn bloodspot screens from ~42,000 children) and saliva samples from ~34,000 children and their parents. These samples enable future research on biomarkers of environmental burden (eg heavy metals, inflammatory markers, epigenetic changes) and help quantify how exposures such as air pollution and heat become biologically embedded. As omics and biomarker technologies advance, these samples will become increasingly valuable for mechanistic EH research.

Simulation and what-if modelling for policy GenV's Intervention Hub and What-If modelling platforms currently under development will allow findings to move from exposure-response estimation to policy simulation. Interventions such as urban greening, traffic reduction or climate adaptation measures can be modelled using GenV's population-representative data to estimate health impacts for specific places and groups before implementation. This supports SDG-aligned economic modelling and spatially targeted policy development.

Population-complete Victorian coverage enabling geographic flexibility GenV includes approximately 30% of all Victorian children born Oct 2021-Oct 2023 across every community and service system. This allows findings to be aggregated to any geographic or administrative unit relevant to EH policy, from local government area to health service region to state. Combined with My Geosome's address-level coverage of all Victorian addresses, GenV provides a uniquely comprehensive and flexible EH data ecosystem with no equivalent in Australia.

Governance and FAIR data infrastructure GenV operates as an Open Science Initiative under multilayered governance including HREC oversight, data access committees and project-specific approvals. Custodianship and research use are clearly separated. Its open science platform and established CVDL linkage pathways ensure data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reproducible, meeting national research infrastructure requirements.

3.5 Recommendations for health data infrastructures

The recommendations below were distilled from stakeholder engagements and a systematic mapping review of recent and freely available publications of environmental epidemiology studies.

Endorsed recommendations	Actions
Integration of Aboriginal Controlled Community Health Organisations and collections of Electronic Medical Records	Establish a sustained multisector program of outreach to build trust and ensure collective benefit of data uses
Cost recovery only for data linkage environments	Build on existing state gov infrastructures: CVDL, CHeReL, etc rather than annual subscription model: SURE, NHDH, etc
Blanket ethics and access approvals for trusted research groups	Develop transparent credentialisation processes and pathway for research groups.
Process for bespoke synthesis of health and population data in exposure areas	Develop process for rapidly summarising health data in flood, fire, smoke, and disaster affected areas, as for ABS statistical boundaries.
Synthetic datasets, encryption and federated learning algorithms	Develop privacy protection technologies using machine learning algorithms
Novel health data aggregates and derived data products	Standardized data custodian approvals process

1. Integration of Aboriginal Controlled Community Health Organisations and collections of Electronic Medical Records

- Data linkage and approvals process for ACCHOs;
- Integration with existing administrative health data portals;
- This will involve a multi-sector program of trust building with remote and aboriginal communities.
- Social license and trust must be earned by respecting traditional customs and ways of being.
- Repeated engagement is required to build rapport.

2. Cost recovery only for data linkage environments

- Cohort survey and administrative data provided in existing government run data linkage environments;
- Cost recovery fee structure for time spent in virtual environments such as the Virtual Access to Linked data (VALT) platform hosted by the Centre for Victorian Data Linkage;
- Infrastructure to support low budget <1-year projects.

3. Blanket ethics and access approvals for trusted research groups

- Periodic ethics re-approvals;
- A system for streamlined data access amendments

4. Process for bespoke synthesis of health and population data in exposure areas

- Non nested non-hierarchical spatial units;
- Health and population data in exposure polygons rather than ABS polygons

5. Synthetic datasets, encryption and federated learning algorithms protect data without undermining precision.

- Synthetic datasets to test analyses and limit time required in linkage environments;

- System for ingesting and geolocating exposure datasets;
- Development of federated learning approach

6. Novel health data aggregates and derived data products

- Collaborations between low risk data infrastructures and data custodians to produce novel health data aggregates and derived data products;
- Standardized data custodian approvals process for geography and time-specific health data aggregates to remove the need for discretionary risk aversion by middle managers;
- Standardised suppression process;
- Five safes training to improve trust between researchers and custodians

Conclusions

This project demonstrated a widely held understanding among Australian researchers of the legal, political and individual privacy risks associated with access to and governance of health data. We conducted a comprehensive survey of EH research experiences seeking precision of epidemiological association discovery and managing the need for secure data linkage environments, data suppression and privacy protection. Our stakeholder engagement revealed a broad range of policy and regulatory practice driven research questions and corresponding research data infrastructures across a spectrum of governance and privacy protections. Specifically, we found broad support for contrasting formulations of space, time, and demographic-aggregated health datasets, such as those compiled and made publicly available by AIHW. Yet, to meet the political and societal mandate of environmental epidemiology, comprehensive databases of person level data and lifestyle information are required for precision of analyses. Horizon scan discussions highlighted the urgent need for streamlined governance, access and ethics processes that diffuse the often-unsurmountable up-front time and financial costs of precision environmental epidemiology. While environmental-health associations can be identified using freely available data and low risk aggregates, the risk of spurious and misleading indications and general lack of confidence in them precludes application in government decision making, especially when litigation is involved. Synthetic datasets may retain epidemiological precision but are often cast into doubt over the methods and approaches to producing them. The federating learning algorithm solution is essentially an attempt to replace human analysts with machine learners. The extent to which these can be trusted

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with sensitive data will be scrutinized very closely by researchers, information security technologists and data custodians.

3.6 Outcomes

Outcome	Indicator/s	Measure	Data Source/s	Baseline and Targets	Results, evidence, and benefits to the research community
Systematic Mapping review of Australian EH research	38 full texts screened	Citations	Google scholar	Baseline: Data infrastructures primarily formulated around health data custodian risk aversion Target: Risk concessions for priority EH research evidence production.	Table 1 summarises a representative sample of literature from the past 5 years. Including exposure outcome pairs and corresponding effect sizes.
Novel lowered risk datasets on platforms AusEnHealth and CARDAT	Mortality and hospitalisation datasets	Number of datasets and time-space trade-offs	CARDAT AusEnHealth	Baseline: 4 mortality datasets are held by CARDAT. Target: 4 New morbidity and mortality data aggregates held by AusEnHealth	Health data aggregates that balance time and space resolution with the need for suppression can be used to produce effect estimates for novel environmental exposures.

3.1. Impact stories

Impact stories would be valuable but were not within the scope of this project.

3.2. Outreach, Communications, and Publications Metrics

Training Activities

Date	Number of attendees	Link to training information or outputs
Example: 20/10/2025	30	https://researchdata.edu.au/parkes-observations-project-semester-2010aprs/445704

Conference and Event Presentations

Date	Links to conference presentation or citation with DOI
Example: 20/10/2021	https://researchdata.edu.au/parkes-observations-project-semester-2010aprs/445704

Published datasets generated by the platform/infrastructure

Date	Link to a Metadata Record or Citation With DOI
Example: 20/10/2021	https://researchdata.edu.au/parkes-observations-project-semester-2010aprs/445704

Publications using data generated by platform/infrastructure

Date	Citation With DOI
Example: July 1999	N. Paskin, "Toward unique identifiers," in Proceedings of the IEEE, vol. 87, no. 7, July 1999. https://doi.org/10.1109/5.771073

Publications that cite/reference the platform/infrastructure

Date	Citation With DOI
Example: July 1999	N. Paskin, "Toward unique identifiers," in Proceedings of the IEEE, vol. 87, no. 7, July 1999. https://doi.org/10.1109/5.771073

Social media mentions of the platform/infrastructure

Date	Link
<i>Example: November 2025</i>	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7396013263328694272/

Blog posts/news articles that reference the platform/infrastructure

Date	Link
<i>Example: November 2025</i>	https://www.qcif.edu.au/news/mapping-hope-for-an-endangered-bird

Implementation of FAIR

Whilst the project has not completed a FIPS profile, the project is seeking a DOI for this report to make the recommendations Findable. In addition, this report recognises areas of FAIRness, e.g. within the GenV and CARDAT

projects that could be adopted across other EH datasets such as the CVDL linkage pathways which ensures that data are Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reproducible.

Additional work to improve the FAIRness of EH data could include combining the strengths of CARDAT (rapid access and derived data), AusEnHealth (governance and aggregated national datasets) and GenV (cohort and individual-level linkage) to build a federated EH platform, which could provide real-time climate feeds, linked health outcomes and modelling tools, such as causal inference. However, this is not within the scope of this project.

4. Lessons Learned

4.1. What Went Well?

Stakeholder engagements across the Healthy Environments and Lives national network were enthusiastically attended and led to several follow-up emails and correspondences. EH researchers were immediately engaged in the aims of the project and were invested in shaping its outcomes. That's because the project plan and aims are timely and promise to facilitate outcomes for environmental epidemiologists, health geographers, environmental policy makers and the Australian public.

4.2. What Could be Improved?

The project was delayed from the outset by the ethics application. Work package dependencies were altered to accommodate shifting timelines, reflecting flexibility of the project governance. The time required to conduct all the stakeholder meetings was underestimated and should have been predictable based on previous experience scheduling meetings.

Risks associated with systematic review screening capacity were perceived early in the project but were not mitigated against concurrent project deadlines and collaborative activities of the HEAL team.

The planned author survey was delivered after the full text screening phase of the systematic mapping review

4.3. Feedback to ARDC (in confidence)

The ARDC have been terrifically supportive and patient through the entire project, valuing quality and integrity of the project execution. It is fully expected that the outcomes of this project will be realised in the coming years through ARDC outreach and activities.

5. References

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